

NOTES

Solution Stability Constants of Nickel(II) Mandelate Complexes

P. V. KHADIKAR* & R. L. AMERIA

Chemical Laboratories, Madhav Science College, Ujjain, (M.P.)

Received 13 March 1972

In continuation of our previous work¹ this communication deals with the determination of stepwise stability constants of nickel(II) mandelate complexes in aqueous solution employing Bjerrum's method². The titration medium was maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1M NaClO₄) and at a temperature of 30° ± 0.2°.

The stepwise stability constants were determined by Bjerrum's method². The aqueous solutions containing perchloric acid plus ligand, and perchloric acid plus ligand plus metal solution, of constant volume (50 ml) and constant ionic strength (0.1 M) due to addition of neutral salt NaClO₄, were titrated against standard alkali at a temperature of 30° ± 0.2°. The *pK_a* value of the ligand, 3.36, as reported by Khadikar³ under the same experimental conditions, was used for the calculations of stability constants of nickel(II) mandelate complexes.

In calculating \bar{n} and [A⁻] the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for \bar{n} and [A⁻] corresponding to different values of *pH* were calculated (Table 1) and the formation curve obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against *p*[A⁻], (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The values of \bar{n} after *pH* 4.25 is almost constant (≈ 2) indicating that under the experimental condition used only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are formed between nickel(II) and mandelic acid. From the formation curve the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, $\log K_{av}$, and $\log \beta_2$ work out to be 2.55, 1.82, 2.05, and 4.37 respectively. The standard deviation of the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, $\log K_{av}$, and $\log \beta_2$ as determined by the method of least squares are found to be ±0.05, ±0.06, ±0.05 and ±0.10 respectively.

* Present address : School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain (M.P.), India.

TABLE 1

Solution stability constants of nickel(II) mandelate complexes

pH	\bar{n}	V_{Tml}	$[H^+] \times 10^3$	$[HA] \times 10^3$	$[A^-] \times 10^3$	$p[A^-]$
2.65	0.10	53.5	2.2400	7.48	1.295	2.889
2.80	0.20	55.0	1.5900	7.29	1.775	2.751
2.95	0.38	56.0	1.1220	7.14	2.470	2.607
3.00	0.52	56.3	1.0000	7.11	2.760	2.559
3.25	0.70	58.5	0.5620	6.84	4.720	2.326
3.50	1.10	60.0	0.3160	6.67	8.190	2.087
3.80	1.55	62.1	0.1590	6.45	15.800	1.801
4.00	1.86	62.4	0.1000	6.41	24.900	1.604
4.25	2.00	63.0	0.0563	6.35	43.800	1.359
4.50	2.03	63.4	0.0316	6.31	77.500	1.111

Thanks are due to Dr. W. V. Bhagwat and Dr. H. N. Sharma for providing facilities, and to the University Grants Commission for the award of a research grant.

REFERENCES

1. P. V. Khadikar and R. L. Ameria, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1201.
2. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, (1941).
3. P. V. Khadikar, Ph.D. Thesis, Vikram University (1967).